

Terpenoids Part XLIII. A New Synthesis of (\pm)- β Bisabolene

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Starting from the key intermediate, 2-methyl-6-(3-keto-cyclohexyl)-2, 6-heptadiene, obtained through two different pathways, a new synthesis of (\pm)- β -bisabolene has been accomplished.

In continuation of our previous synthetic studies¹⁻³ employing β -ketosulphoxides as the key intermediates for the preparation of appropriate ketones and diketones which can be converted into the desired terpenic compounds through certain well-known reactions, we wish to report the synthesis of (\pm)- β bisabolene.

β -Bisabolene, a sesquiterpenic hydrocarbon, has been found to occur in bergamot, carrot and rhizomes of *Petasites officinalis* Moench oils⁴ along with its other isomers.

On the basis of chemical reactions and spectral data⁵, it has been assigned the constitution (I). Birch and Murray⁶ have converted lanceol into β -bisabolene through hydrogenolysis. Simultaneously two syntheses^{7,8} of this hydrocarbon have been reported from the same intermediate compound (II), 2-methyl-6-keto-6-(4-methyl- Δ^3 -cyclohexenyl)- Δ^2 -hexene, by taking advantage of the Wittig reaction⁹ for the creation of

methylene bond in the bisabolene skeleton. Another synthesis of β -bisabolene accomplished by Vig et al¹⁰ utilises the Wittig reaction for the fixation of isopropylidene bond.

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In the present studies another clean synthesis of this hydrocarbon has been described starting from the cardinal intermediate, 2-methyl-6-(3-keto-cyclohexyl)-2, 6-heptadiene (XI), obtained through the sequence of reactions depicted below:-

3-Carbethoxy-1:1-ethylenedioxy cyclohexane (III) with methyl sulphanyl carbanion¹¹ in anhydrous tetrahydrofuran under nitrogen atmosphere afforded β -keto-sulphoxide (IV) in 83 percent yield. This compound showed the presence of sulphur through Lassaigne's test. Alkylation¹² of the β -ketosulphoxide (IV) with isoprene bromide in D. M. F. using sodium hydride as a base followed by the reduction¹¹ of the alkylated β -ketosulphoxide (V) (which was not isolated) with aluminium-amalgam in tetrahydrofuran furnished ketal-ketone (VI) in 70 percent yield. The compound (VI) when subjected to Wittig reaction⁹ with methylene phosphorane under nitrogen atmosphere yielded 2-methyl-6-(3:3-ethylenedioxy cyclohexyl)-2, 6-heptadiene (X) in 80 percent yield. The methylenic-ketal (X) was also achieved through a different route starting from 2-(3:3-ethylenedioxy cyclohexyl)-allyl alcohol¹³ (VII) which was converted into its vinyl ether (VIII) by mercuric acetate catalysed *trans*-etherification¹⁴ with ethyl vinyl ether. The purified 2-(3:3-ethylenedioxy cyclohexyl)-allyl vinyl ether (VIII) on Claisen rearrangement¹⁵ provided 4-(3:3-ethylenedioxy cyclohexyl)-4-pentenal (IX) in 85 percent yield. The aldehyde (IX) was subjected to Wittig reaction⁹ with isopropyltriphenyl-

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phosphonium iodide under the usual conditions to give the ketal (X) in 70% yield. The ketal (X) prepared above through two different ways after purification through chromatography showed superimposable I. R. spectra.

2 Methyl-6-(3:3-ethylenedioxy cyclohexyl)-2, 6-heptadiene (X) on deketalisation with dilute hydrochloric acid in acetone led to the formation of 2-methyl-6-(3-ketocyclohexyl)-2, 6-heptadiene (XI) in 76 percent yield. Formylation¹⁶ of the ketone (XI) with ethyl formate in the presence of sodium hydride at low temperature provided 2-methyl-6-(4-formyl-3-ketocyclohexyl)-2, 6-heptadiene (XII) in 71 percent yield. It gave violet colouration with ferric chloride solution. The compound (XII, when subjected to lithium aluminium hydride reduction afforded a mixture of alcohols¹⁷ (XIII) and (XIV). However, no attempt was made to separate the two allylic carbinols as both on treatment with phosphorous tribromide in dry ether afforded the same allylic bromide^{18,19} (XV).

The bromide (XV) on reduction with lithium aluminium hydride in anhydrous ether yielded (\pm)- β -bisabolene (I) which was purified through chromatography. The identity of the synthesised hydrocarbon (I) was confirmed through the comparison of I. R. spectrum with that of previously synthesised (\pm)- β -bisabolene^{7,10}.

EXPERIMENTAL*

1-(3:3-ethylenedioxcyclohexyl)-1-keto-2 methyl sulphanyl ethyl (IV)

Methyl sulphanyl carbanion was prepared from sodium hydride (1.8 g.) and dimethyl sulphoxide (19.3 ml.) under nitrogen atmosphere. An equal volume of dry T.H.F. was added and the contents cooled in an ice bath. 3-Carbethoxy-1:1-ethylenedioxy cyclohexane (III, 4.0 g.) was added dropwise with stirring over a period of several minutes. The ice-bath was removed and the stirring continued for an hour more at the room temperature. The reaction mixture was then poured into three times its volume of water, acidified at 0° with hydrochloric acid (7.6 ml.) and thoroughly extracted with chloroform. The combined extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated to obtain β -ketosulphoxide (IV, 3.8 g.), as a viscous oil, in 93 percent yield. It gave the test of sulphur. However, no attempt was made to isolate this compound and was used as such for further reaction.

5-Methyl-1-(3:3-ethylenedioxcyclohexyl)-4-hexenone-1 (VI):

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* Boiling points are uncorrected. I. R. spectra were recorded on Perking-Elmer infracord with sodium chloride optics using thin liquid film.

Sodium hydride (0.65 g.) in dimethyl formamide (15 ml.) was placed under nitrogen atmosphere. To this cooled slurry was added dropwise, during stirring, the β -ketosulphoxide (IV, 3.5 g.) in dimethyl formamide and the stirring continued till the evolution of hydrogen gas had ceased. To the reaction mixture was added dropwise isoprene bromide (2.15 g.) and the contents were stirred for additional half an hour at room temperature. The product was diluted with water (100 ml.), extracted with chloroform, washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After evaporation of the solvent, 3.8 g. of the alkylated β -ketosulphoxide (V) (which was not isolated) was dissolved in aqueous T. H. F. (240 ml; 10%). Freshly prepared small pieces of aluminium amalgam was introduced to the stirred contents and then heated at 65° for about 2 hr. The reaction mixture was then filtered and the residual solid washed many times with T. H. F. The filtrate was concentrated to remove most of the T. H. F. and the residue was taken up in ether. The extract was dried over sodium sulphate and evaporated to leave an oil which was distilled under reduced pressure to furnish 5-methyl-1-(3:3 ethylenedioxcyclohexyl)-4-hexenone 1 (VI), b.p. 152-54°/5mm. yield 2.2 g. (87 percent); η_D^{18-5} 1.4830. (Found: C, 70.97; H, 9.13. $C_{15}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 71.39; H, 9.59%).

Infrared spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 1720 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$), 1090 cm^{-1} (ketal), 815, 840 cm^{-1} ($R_1R_2C=CHR_3$) and other bands at 2900, 1460, 1375, 1170, 1040, 950, and 920 cm^{-1} .

2-Methyl 6-(3:3-ethylenedioxcyclohexyl)-2, 6-heptadiene (X):

Methylenephosphorane was obtained from sodium hydride (0.2 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (4.4 ml.) and methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (3.5 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (8.8 ml.) under nitrogen atmosphere. To the phosphorane was added the ketone (VI, 2.0 g.) in tetrahydrofuran (5 ml) at room temperature. The contents were stirred for 3 hr. at room temperature and left overnight. The reaction mixture was poured into cold water (40 ml.) and the organic layer taken in petroleum ether (40-60°) and washed thrice with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and solvent removed. The residue was chromatographed over alumina to furnish the hydrocarbon (X) on elution with petroleum ether (40-60°) (60 ml.). This was further purified by distillation under reduced pressure, b.p. 145°/6 mm; yield 1.5 g. (75%); η_D^{18-5} 1.4900. (Found: C, 76.26; H, 9.98. $C_{16}H_{26}O_2$ requires C, 76.75; H, 10.47%).

Infrared spectrum showed absence of any absorption in the carbonyl region. Characteristic peaks at 1090 cm^{-1} (ketal), 1650, 890 cm^{-1} (methylene), 812 and 840 cm^{-1} ($R_1R_2C=CHR_3$). Other bands at 1615, 1450, 1375, 1320, 1200, 1175, 1045, 975, 960 and 920 cm^{-1} .

2-(3:3 ethylenedioxcyclohexyl)-allyl vinyl ether (VIII) :

A mixture of ethyl vinyl ether (50 g.), 2-(3:3-ethylenedioxcyclohexyl)-allyl alcohol (VII, 10.0 g.) and anhydrous mercuric acetate (0.68 g.) (freshly crystallised from absolute ethanol) was refluxed for 9 hr. The product after chilling in ice was mixed with cold aqueous sodium carbonate (36 g., 10 percent) and the mixture stirred for 30

min. at 0°, organic layer separated and dried (anhydrous K_2CO_3). Removal of the solvent and chromatography of the residue on alumina (80 g.) furnished on elution with petroleum ether (40-60°, 80 ml.), the vinyl ether (VIII) which was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 130-35°/6 mm; yield 7.0 g. (88%); $\eta^{18.5}$ 1.4670. (Found: C, 69.14; H, 8.47. $C_{13}H_{20}O_9$ requires C, 69.61; H, 8.99%).

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I. R. spectrum showed characteristic bands at 1640, 1170 cm^{-1} (vinyl ether), 1090, 1040 cm^{-1} (ketal), 920 cm^{-1} (terminal methylene) and other prominent peaks at 1450, 1375, 1300, 1200 and 950 cm^{-1} .

4-(3:3-ethylenedioxcyclohexyl)-4-pentenal (IX) :

The vinyl ether (VIII, 7.0 g.) was heated for 45 min. at 180° under nitrogen atmosphere in a fully immersed half-filled sealed tube. Direct distillation provided 6.0 g. (85 percent) of the aldehyde (IX); b. p. 145°/5 mm.; $\eta^{18.5}$ 1.4760. (Found: C,

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69.15; H, 8.43. $C_{13}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 69.61; H, 8.99%).

I. R. spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 2720, 1740 cm^{-1} (sat. -CHO), 3090, 1560, 920, 890 cm^{-1} (terminal methylene) 1090, 1035 cm^{-1} (ketal) and other peaks at 1615, 1450, 1360, 1200, 1155 and 950 cm^{-1} .

2-Methyl-6-(3:3-ethylenedioxcyclohexyl)-2, 6-heptadiene (X) :-

To the phosphorane, at room temperature, prepared from sodium hydride (1.3 g.) in dimethylsulphoxide (14 ml.) and isopropyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (11.6 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (28 ml.) under nitrogen atmosphere, was added the aldehyde (IX, 5.5 g.) with occasionally shaking and warmed to 45° for 1 hr. The contents were stirred for 3 hr. at room temperature and left overnight. The reaction mixture was poured into cold water and worked up in the usual manner to obtain (X); b. p. 150-45°/5 mm.; yield 6.0 g. (70%). (Found: C, 70.98; H, 9.16. $C_{15}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 71.39; H, 9.59%).

I.R. spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 1650, 1615, 1450, 1375, 1320, 1200, 1175, 1045, 975, 920, 840 and 812 cm^{-1} .

2 Methyl-6-(3-keto-cyclohexyl)-2, 6-heptadiene (XI) :-

The ketal (X), (4.0 g.) was dissolved in acetone (64 ml.) and mixed with aqueous hydrochloric acid (10 percent; 16 ml.). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 3 hr. The contents were diluted with saturated sodium chloride solution and the product taken up in ether, dried (Na_2SO_4), solvent removed and the residue distilled under reduced pressure to give the ketone (XI); yield 2.5 g. (76 percent) b. p. 135-38°/5 mm. $\eta^{18.5}$ 1.4850.

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(Found: C, 81.13; H, 10.45. $C_{14}H_{22}O$ requires C, 81.50; H, 10.75%).

I. R. spectrum showed peaks at 1718 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$), 3090, 1650, 890 cm^{-1} (terminal methylene) and 840 cm^{-1} ($R_1R_2C=CHR_3$) and other prominent bands at 2920, 1450, 1375, 1320, 1220 cm^{-1} .

2-Methyl 6-(4-formyl-3-keto-cyclohexyl)-2, 6-heptadiene (XII) :-

To a cooled suspension of sodium hydride (0.35 g.) in dry benzene (50 ml.) was added dropwise with stirring, ethyl formate (4.5 g) during 30 min. followed by the addition of the ketone (XI, 3.0 g.) over a period of 20 min. After stirring for 1 hr. more at room temperature, the contents were left overnight. The reaction mixture was decomposed with cold water, aqueous layer separated and the benzene layer washed 2-3 times with cold 5 percent sodium hydroxide solution. The combined aqueous extract was acidified with hydrochloric acid and the oil taken up in ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and distilled under reduced pressure; b. p. 145-50°/5 mm; yield 2.5 g. (71%); η^{17}_D 1.4880. It gave a violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 76.46; H, 8.89. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 76.88; H, 9.66%).

Reduction of 2-methyl-6-(4-formyl-3-keto-cyclohexyl)-2, 6-heptadiene (XII) :-

To a well stirred suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (0.54 g) in dry ether (200 ml.), was introduced 2-methyl-6 (4 formyl-3-keto-cyclohexyl)-2, 6-heptadiene (XII; 5.0 g.) in dry ether (100 ml.) at such a rate so as to maintain ether at a gentle reflux. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux overnight with constant stirring. It was cooled and hydrolysed with sodium carbonate solution (20% ; 100 ml.). The ether solution was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and removal of the solvent followed by *vacuo* distillation gave a mixture of 2-methyl-6-(4-methanol-3-cyclohexenyl)-2, 6-heptadiene (XIII) and 2-methyl-6-(4-methylene-3-cyclohexenyl)-2-, 6-heptadiene (XIV), b.p.105-21/8 m.m. (Found: C, 81.29; H, 10.46. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}$ requires C, 81.76; H, 10.98%).

2-Methyl-6-(4-methyl bromide-3 cyclohexenyl)-2, 6-heptadiene (XV) :-

The mixture of the above alcohols (2.5 g.) in dry ether (150 ml.) was treated dropwise with phosphorous tribromide (1.3 g.) during half an hour in the dark. The solution was refluxed for 3 hr., cooled and poured into ice-water, shaken and extracted with ether (3 x 50 ml.). The ether extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water (twice) and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After the evaporation of the solvent, there was obtained the bromide (XV) (2.8 g; 86 percent) which was not distilled and used for further reaction.

2-Methyl-6-(4-methyl-3-cyclohexenyl)-2, 6-heptadiene (I) :-

2-Methyl-6-(4 methyl bromide-cyclohexene-3)-2, 6-heptadiene (XV) (2.5 g.) in dry ether (10 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred slurry of lithium aluminium hydride (0.25 g.) in ether (100 ml.) and the mixture was further stirred for 3 hr. under reflux. Thereafter, the contents were cooled and the metal complex decomposed by the addition of sodium pot. tartrate solution (25 ml; 20 percent). The ether layer was separated and the aqueous phase extracted with ether (3 x 100 ml.). After drying, the combined extract over sodium sulphate and evaporation of the solvent, the residue was passed through alumina column (30 g.) using petroleum ether (40-60°) as elutant. The petroleum ether fraction (60 ml.) after removing the solvent was distilled under reduced pressure to

afford (\pm)- β -bisabolene (I); b. p. 112-14°/5 mm; yield 1.5. g. (69%); η_D^{20} 1.4921 (lit.¹⁰ η_D^{20} 1.4923). Found: C, 87.98; H, 11.67. C₁₅H₂₄ requires C, 88.16; H, 11.84%.

I. R. spectrum of the synthetic hydrocarbon (I) showed prominent bands at 2875, 1650, 1450, 1380, 1150, 1020, 911, 890, 815 and 800 cm⁻¹ are identical to those given in literature^{7,10} for (\pm)- β -bisabolene at 2875, 1650, 1450, 1385, 1150, 1020, 909, 890, 830 and 800 cm⁻¹

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